

Surface Chemistry of Amphipathic Graft Copolymer Stabilizers in Polymethyl Methacrylate Organosols*

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Received 4 September 1972

The intrinsic stabilizing capacity of two amphipathic polymeric organosol stabilizers has been assessed. A "feather"-type molecule, whose lyophilic portions were based on polylauryl methacrylate (LMA), was found to stabilize ca. 2.6×10^6 cm² per gram of polymer adsorbed. A "comb"-type molecule, whose lyophilic moieties were based on poly-12-hydroxy stearic acid (PSA), stabilized ca. 1.6×10^6 cm² per gram. We propose that the superior performance of the "feather"-like polymer arises from its greater density of lyophilic chain segments in the solvated layer which it creates at the sol particle/diluent interface. Entropic factors are probably responsible for a higher repulsive potential upon inter-particle collisions.

We have confirmed the findings of Osmond and Walbridge that the surface concentration of stabilizing groups is relatively independent of organosol particle size and total surface area, in spite of the fact that we used different techniques in the synthesis of both organosols and LMA stabilizer.

These results also support our previously proposed mechanism of particle formation of polymer colloids, both aqueous and organic, in which homogeneous nucleation and limited flocculation determine the final particle concentration.

Polymer organosols are colloidal dispersions of polymers in organic media. Some of the earliest stable dispersions of polymethyl methacrylate in hydrocarbon media were made by Osmond¹. These were prepared by the polymerization of methyl methacrylate in a solution of degraded rubber in hydrocarbon solvent using benzoyl peroxide as initiator. Amphipathic graft copolymers were formed "in situ" and were evidently bound onto the surface of the particles subsequently formed. The lyophobic moiety (PMMA) of the graft copolymer was presumed to be anchored onto the particle surface, and the lyophilic moiety (degraded rubber), solvated by the medium, as shown below :

* Dedicated to Prof. Santi R. Palit on the occasion of his 60th birth anniversary.

The colloidal particles so formed are thus stabilized by this lyophilic polymeric layer. The flocculation barrier in these systems results from "osmotic" repulsions generated by the compression of solvated moieties when particles approach each other².

The stability of the organosols prepared by the above method was not reproducible because of the unpredictable nature of the "in situ" grafting process. Excessive grafting presumably reduced the thickness of the barrier by flattening the molecule on the particle surface leading to instability. To overcome this problem Osmond and coworkers^{3,4} developed amphipathic polymeric stabilizers, and we have used two of these. The structure of each is schematically given below :

- 1) Lauryl methacrylate (LMA) graft-copoly methyl methacrylate stabilizer:

- 2) Poly-12-hydroxy stearate (PSA) graft-copoly methyl methacrylate stabilizer:

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Organosols : Organosols with LMA stabilizer were prepared in a two necked round bottom flask, one neck of which was filled with a serum cap. A solution of the stabilizer, MMA and *n*-heptane in this flask was thoroughly degassed by "freeze-thawing" on a vacuum line. The initiators were injected from a hypodermic syringe through the serum cap, and the mixture was stirred for 48 hrs. The amount of polymer formed was found by determining the difference between the non volatile matter (NVM) contents of the starting solution and the organosol.

Organosols with PSA stabilizer were obtained from dilatometric experiments designed to study particle formation and polymerization kinetics. The conversion was calculated from the volume contraction at the time the sample was taken. The NVM content of the starting solution was determined gravimetrically.

Determination of NVM Content : Samples were weighed into weighing bottles containing a definite amount of hydroquinone (to prevent further polymerization). Each sample was heated under vacuum at 50° for 4 hrs. in order to achieve constant weight.

Ultracentrifugation of Organosols : Samples of about 15 ml of the organosols were spun down in an International Preparative Ultracentrifuge, Model B-60 at a temperature of 16°. Organosols with LMA stabilizer were spun at 15,000 rpm for 60 min. Organosols with PSA stabilizer were spun at 25,000 rpm for 90 min. This was necessary because of

the smaller particle size of the PSA-stabilized latexes. The supernatant serum was isolated with a syringe.

Particle Size of Organosols : The particle size of the organosols was determined by means of an Hitachi HU-11A electron microscope. The particles were supported on carbon films prepared by standard techniques⁵. In the case of LMA-stabilized organosols, shadow casting was not necessary because of their large particle size (about 0.1μ), whereas in the case of PSA-stabilized organosols, shadow casting with Pt/C was necessary because of lower particle size (about 0.03μ). The surface average diameter, given by $\Sigma n_j D_j^3 / \Sigma n_j D_j^2$, was used in all of our subsequent calculation.

Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC) of the Stabilizers in the Sera : Samples for GPC investigation were prepared by removing all hydrocarbon diluent from the sera under vacuum at 50° for 4 hr. Solutions were made up in tetrahydrofuran (THF) to a concentration of about 4 mg/ml. The exact concentrations were known. The chromatographic runs were made on a Waters "Ana-Prep" GPC using porous glass beads as the stationary phase and THF as the mobile phase. A set of four $4' \times \frac{1}{2}''$ diameter columns were used with glass beads of the following pore sizes : 75\AA , 374\AA , 1250\AA , 2000\AA . The sera from the LMA-stabilized dispersions were run on these columns. Since the above columns did not have high enough resolution at low molecular weights, the sera from PSA-stabilized sols were run on a $8' \times \frac{1}{2}''$ diameter column packed with glass beads of 50\AA pore size.

RESULTS

Stabilizer Adsorption : A summary of the experimentally found surface concentrations and surface layer packing densities of the stabilizer molecules in the two systems is given in Table 1. The weight of the "soluble moiety" of the stabilizer reported is one half of the weight of stabilizer adsorbed because the lyophobe : lyophile balance is 1 : 1 by weight. The stabilizer barrier thickness was calculated assuming that the adsorbed stabilizer forms a uniform sheath on the surface of the particle, from the following equation :

$$\frac{N\pi}{6}(\bar{D}_s^3 - \bar{X}_s^3) = \frac{W}{\rho_{stab}}$$

where N is the number of particles,

\bar{D}_s , the measured surface-average diameter,

W , the weight of the stabilizer adsorbed,

ρ_{stab} is the density of the stabilizer, and

\bar{X}_s is the diameter of the PMMA kernel, calculated from the mass of polymer formed and the number of particles.

TABLE I
Surface Coverage of PMMA Organosol Particles by Polymeric Stabilizers : Gravimetric Results

LMA Stabilizer														
Exp. No.	Initial NVM g	NVM Serum g	NVM Organo-sol g	% Conversion**	Polymer Formed g	Stabr.* Adsorb. bed g	% Orig. Stabr. bed	\bar{D}^s Å	$N_e/l \times 10^{-15}$	\bar{X}_s Å	Stabr.*** Barrier Thickness g	Weight Sol. Moiety g	Total Surface From \bar{X}_s cm ²	Area stabilized per soluble moiety Å ²
1	8.00	7.80	14.28	38	6.28	1.02	12.7	1145	7.64	1098	23.5	0.51	2.78×10^6	3400
2	6.20	6.05	11.80	34	5.60	0.93	15.0	1184	6.01	1145	19.5	0.47	2.40×10^6	3200
3	3.95	3.82	8.77	29	4.82	0.87	21.0	1217	4.65	1187	15.0	0.44	2.01×10^6	2900
4	2.06	2.04	6.00	23	3.94	0.63	30.6	floc'd	—	—	—	—	—	—
PSA Stabilizer $\times 10^{-16}$														
5	1.53	0.68	—	5.00	0.634	0.860	56.2	328	4.88	242	43	0.430	1.33×10^6	83
6	2.79	0.60	—	16.51	2.092	2.217	78.2	347	4.10	268	40	1.108	3.96×10^6	96
7	4.39	0.74	—	14.93	1.892	3.691	82.0	266	9.24	181	43	1.845	5.29×10^6	77
8	8.17	2.41	—	27.60	3.497	5.983	73.2	233	13.70	164	35	2.991	10.80×10^6	100

Initial Experimental Conditions

LMA Organosols :

[M] = 1.24
 [CHP] = 2.85×10^{-2}
 [DDM] = 1.32×10^{-2}
 $R_t = 1.2 \times 10^{14}$ Mole c/l sec.

PSA Organosols :

[M] = 0.915
 [CHP] = 2.58×10^{-2}
 [DDM] = 1.25×10^{-2}
 $R_t = 1.07 \times 10^{14}$ Mole c/l sec.

* Refer to Table 3.

** Conversions obtained gravimetrically for Exp. Nos. 1-4 and dilatometrically for Nos. 5-8.

*** Dry basis.

The surface-average number of particles, \bar{N}_s , was calculated from the following equation :

$$\bar{N}_s = \left(\frac{w}{\rho_{stab}} + \frac{w'}{\rho_{PMMA}} \right) \times \frac{6}{\pi(\bar{D}_s)^3}$$

where w' is the amount of PMMA formed, and ρ_{PMMA} is the polymer density. The density of the stabilizer solids was calculated from the measured density of the stabilizer solution assuming volume-additivity of the components.

Molecular Weight-Selectivity of Adsorption : The organosols were ultracentrifuged to remove all particles, whereupon the sera were analyzed by gel permeation chromatography (GPC). The chances of desorption of stabilizer molecules during centrifugation are assumed to be negligible⁶. The GPC curves for the LMA stabilizer and for the sera from Experiments 1 through 4 are shown in Figures 1 through 5 respectively. The outer envelope in each case represents the experimental curve, while the internal, dotted curves are four arbitrarily chosen components whose sum comprises the total envelope. These were computed with a DuPont Curve Analyzer.

Fig. 1. (LMA Stabilizer).

Fig. 2. (Serum 1).

Fig. 3. (Serum 2).

Fig. 4. (Serum 3).

Qualitatively it can be seen from Figs. 1-5 that the highest molecular weight component is selectively adsorbed, almost to the exclusion of the lower molecular weight fractions. Table 2 summarizes the quantitative analysis of the GPC curves. These data, along with the gravimetric analyses of the sera and stabilizer solutions allowed us to calculate by difference exactly how much of each component was adsorbed (Table 3). From Table 3 it is evident that rather low percentages of the high molecular weight fraction were adsorbed (23-38%), and that in Exp. No. 4, a total of at least 0.63 g or 31% of the stabilizer was adsorbed. The negative differences in mass sometimes found for peaks (2+3) and 4 indicate

Fig. 5. (Serum 4).

that small amounts of low molecular weight soluble polymer were formed during the polymerization.

TABLE 2

Molecular-Weight-Selectivity of Adsorption of LMA Stabilizer: GPC Component peak areas

GPC areas expressed as percent of total curve envelope of sera taken after ultracentrifugation of organosols

Estimated weight-average molecular weights of component peak stabilizer polymers:

Exp. No.	Component peak No.			Fig. No.	Peak No.	$\bar{M}_w \times 10^{-5}$
	1	2 & 3	4			
1	47	41	12	2	1	11
2	44	39	17	3	2	3.0
3	41	32	27	4	3	1.4
4	35	28	36	5	4	0.57
Original Stabilizer	55	37	8	1		

TABLE 3

MW Selectivity of Adsorption of LMA Stabilizer Components : GPC Data

(N.B. : Calculations normalized to 100 g of Starting Solution.)

Exp. No.	Description	Experimental NVM Content g	Weight of components, g (Derived from areas under GPC Curves)			Total Stabilizer Adsorbed g
			Peak 1	Peak 2&3	Peak 4	
1	Starting sol'n	8	4.43	2.92	0.65	
	Serum 1	7.8	3.42	2.98	0.91	
	Difference		1.02	-0.063	-0.26	1.02
	Percent adsorbed		23	0	0	
2	Starting sol'n	6.2	3.43	2.26	0.50	
	Serum 2	6.05	2.52	2.25	1.00	
	Difference		0.92	0.013	-0.50	0.93
	Percent adsorbed		27	0	0	
3	Starting sol'n	3.95	2.19	1.44	0.32	
	Serum 3	3.82	1.55	1.21	1.00	
	Difference		0.64	0.23	-0.68	0.87
	Percent adsorbed		29	16	0	
4	Starting sol'n	2.06	1.14	0.75	0.17	
	Serum 4	2.04	0.71	0.55	0.72	
	Difference		0.43	0.20	-0.55	0.63
	Percent adsorbed		38	27	0	

In the case of the PSA stabilizer we see exactly the same kind of molecular weight selectivity. GPC analysis of the sera after ultracentrifugation of the organosols from Exp. Nos. 5, 7 and 8 again show that the high molecular weight components are preferentially bound to the surface of the polymer particles. The chromatograms are shown in Figures 7, 8 and 9 respectively and may be compared with that for the original PSA stabilizer, shown in Figure 6. It should be kept in mind that these represent the unadsorbed stabilizer. We may deduce the molecular weight distribution of the adsorbed polymer by taking the difference between each of the chromatograms in Figures 7, 8 and 9 and in Figure 6. It can be seen that as the initial concentration of stabilizer is increased, selectivity becomes greater. Reference to Table 1 shows that the apparent efficiency of adsorption of the PSA stabilizer is much greater than that of the LMA, since up to 82% of the PSA stabilizer is adsorbed.

Compositional Selectivity of Adsorption : The GPC theoretically separates molecules solely according to size. To determine to what extent compositional selectivity of adsorption might accompany molecular weight selectivity, infrared spectra were taken of serum fractions from Exp. No. 4. Two fractions, between counts 30 and 35 (low molecular weight) were obtained by repeated runs on the analytical GPC column. The IR spectra of these fractions were compared with similar fractions of the original LMA stabilizer. Spectra of the low molecular weight fractions are shown in Figure 10. Both high molecular weight fractions had spectra almost identical to the upper curve in Fig. 10, and are not shown.

Fig. 6.

Fig. 7.

Fig. 8.

Fig. 9.

Fig. 10.

On the other hand, the low polymer serum fraction is considerably less polar in character than the corresponding fraction of original stabilizer. For instance, the ratio of absorbance for C = O stretching at 1750 cm^{-1} to that for C-H stretching at 2930 cm^{-1} is 0.69 for the

TABLE 4

*Molecular Weight Selectivity of Adsorption of PSA Stabilizer :
GPC Component Peak Areas*

Areas expressed as percent of total curve envelope of GPC chromatograms of sera taken after ultracentrifugation of organosols

Experiment No.	Component Peak No.				Fig. No.	Peak Positions, Counts :	
	1	2	3	4		Peak No.	Counts
5	1.7	0	28	70	7	1	12
7	11	13	48	29	8	2	13
8	13	22	39	26	9	3	14.5
Original Stabilizer	29	20	44	7.3	6	4	17

TABLE 5

Comparison of IR Spectra of High and Low Molecular Weight Fractions of LMA Stabilizer before and after Adsorption

Ratio of Given Absorbance to C-H Absorbance

	Sample	Cm^{-1} 2930 C-H	1750 C = O	1470 C-CH ₃	1160 ester	975 COOH	705 (C-S-C ?)
Fraction 1	Stabilizer	1.00	1.05	0.42	0.76	0.21	0.10
High MW	Serum	1.00	1.00	0.44	0.72	0.24	0.13
Fraction 2	Stabilizer	1.00	1.13	0.42	0.73	0.20	0.08
Low MW	Serum	1.00	0.69	0.40	0.47	0.15	0.14

Fraction 1 : High MW cut from GPC between counts 30 & 35.

Fraction 2 : Low MW cut from GPC between counts 35 & 39.

Serum obtained after Ultra-Centrifugation of Polymer from Exp. No. 4.

serum low polymer versus 1-13, almost double, for the original stabilizer. Similar behavior is observed for the ester band at 1160 cm^{-1} and for COOH at 975 cm^{-1} . The data in Table 3 show that 0.55 g of low molecular weight, soluble polymer (component 4) was formed during the polymerization in Exp. No. 4. This may have arisen as a result of chain transfer of oligomeric radicals with the dodecylmercaptan present in the initiator system. The increase in IR absorbance at 705 cm^{-1} supports this view. We may conclude that there is no compositional selectivity due to adsorption in the LMA stabilizer system.

Surface Density of Adsorbed Stabilizers : The efficiency of a stabilizer may best be measured by the extent of the surface each active group stabilizes. In this case the active groups are the lyophilic moieties, or side chains, of the amphipathic stabilizer molecules. Electron microscopy was used to obtain the average polymer organosol particle size, from

which, along with the known volume of polymer formed, the number of particles could be calculated. The size distributions were broad, so that the surface-average diameter was used. From the total particle surface area and the amount of stabilizer adsorbed, the area occupied per soluble moiety was found and reported in table 1. These are 2900 to 3400 Å² for the LMA stabilizer (each soluble moiety of which had an average molecular weight of ca. 37,500) and 80 to 100 Å² for the PSA stabilizer (molecular weight of soluble moiety, ca. 1500). The data from table 1 show that slightly more surface area per soluble moiety is obtained as the initial stabilizer concentration is increased.

When the efficiencies of the two different stabilizers are compared, the data in Table 1 for Exp. Nos. 1 and 8, in which the initial amounts of stabilizer are almost the same, show that the PSA stabilized four times as much surface as the LMA (10.8×10^6 cm² vs. 2.78×10^6 cm²). However when they are compared in terms of area stabilized *per gram of stabilizer adsorbed*, the two are almost equal in efficiency: 2.7×10^6 cm²/g for the LMA vs. 1.8×10^6 cm²/g for the PSA, with the LMA being somewhat more efficient.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Several aspects of the surface chemistry of polymeric amphipathic stabilizers, first described in the British patent literature by Osmond, Waite and Walbridge, have been investigated. Both the LMA and PSA stabilizers, when prepared as described, have broad, poly-modal molecular weight distributions. We have found that the higher molecular weight fractions are preferentially adsorbed. The stabilizing efficiency of the PSA is approximately four times that of the LMA in terms of polymer surface stabilized per gram of stabilizer used as described in the patents. In terms of surface stabilized per gram of stabilizer absorbed, however, the LMA is somewhat better. There is apparently little compositional selectivity upon adsorption of the stabilizer.

Since the backbones of both stabilizers are almost the same, differences in their performance may be attributed to entropic and/or enthalpic factors in grafted side chains. In both stabilizers the lyophilic moieties may be considered as mostly polymethylene-like so that enthalpic interactions with the diluent will be of the same magnitude, to a first approximation. Therefore any differences in stabilizing efficiency may be attributed to configurational differences. The LMA is comprised of highly branched C₁₂ tertiary chains along methacrylate secondary chains, which in turn are fastened at random points to the primary, PMMA "anchor" chain. These are best described as "feather" polymers. Our synthesis of this type of stabilizer differs slightly from that prescribed by Osmond and coworkers in that it is entirely pre-formed prior to the latex polymerization, rather than being formed *in situ*. The PSA stabilizer probably has a somewhat lower segment density of soluble moieties because of shorter and less frequent C₆ branches. It has been described by its inventors as a "comb" polymer.

The magnitude of the potential energy barrier to flocculation is thus probably somewhat greater for the "feather" polymer because of its greater segment density. The somewhat larger area stabilized per gram of polymer supports this contention. Comparative studies on the stabilities of the two types of latexes would help to resolve this question.

Our results on surface coverage are to be compared with those of Osmond and Walbridge⁷ who studied the same two stabilizers (with difference in synthesis of the LMA noted above). We support their major findings that : (1) the area stabilized per soluble moiety is approximately constant for each type of stabilizer regardless of particle size; (2) the configuration of the PSA chains must be essentially extended normal to the surface. Each PSA side chain occupies a cylindrical volume of approximately 90 \AA^3 in cross-section, which is roughly one third that found by Osmond and Walbridge; (3) the configuration of the LMA chains, on the other hand, is more random, assuming a shape more like flattened disks about 3000 \AA^2 in area and of about half the barrier thickness of a PSA surface layer. Again this area is one-third of Osmond and Walbridge's minimum value for this stabilizer on a PMMA/MA (98 : 2) copolymer surface. However, the ratio of area occupied by LMA to that occupied by PSA is somewhat more than 30, as the previous authors also found. Our smaller absolute values for the areas are probably attributable to the lower temperature, 30° , which we used compared to their 50° - 90° . This also undoubtedly means that we have very much less grafting of stabilizer molecule to the particle surface.

These results support our model for the homogeneous mechanism of particle nucleation in polymer colloids^{5, 8}. When stabilizer is present in only small amounts, limited flocculation becomes the primary factor in determining the final concentration of latex particles. As new particles are formed, stabilizer is adsorbed onto the new and growing interface until the reservoir of dissolved stabilizer in the continuous medium is depleted. Thereafter, any new interface formed is unstable and will disappear by flocculation. Thus the total surface of the final dispersion will be that area which corresponds to the "intrinsic stabilizing capacity" and the amount of the stabilizer present, as shown by Roe⁹. We have found that in electrostatically stabilized aqueous latexes the surface charge density at the stage during polymerization when new particles are no longer formed, is constant regardless of particle size, in direct analogy to our findings here.

Acknowledgement : This work was supported in part by a grant from S. C. Johnson & Sons, Inc.

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